

Project Title	Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice
Project Acronym	WorldFAIR
Grant Agreement No	101058393
Instrument	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01
Topic, type of action	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-41 HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Start Date of Project	2022-06-01
Duration of Project	24 months
Project Website	http://worldfair-project.eu

D6.3 Pilot Testing Harmonisation Workflows

Work Package	WP6 - Social Surveys
Lead Author (Org)	Steven McEachern (Australian Data Archive)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Hilde Orten (Sikt), Ryan Perry (Australian Data Archive), Kristina Strand (Sikt)
Due Date	29.02.2024

Date	29.02.2024
Version	1 DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10724744

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
0.1	09.02.2024	Steven McEachern, Hilde Orten, Ryan Perry, Kristina Strand	Draft for internal review
0.2	28.02.2024	Steven McEachern, Hilde Orten, Ryan Perry, Kristina Strand	Submitted final version

Disclaimer

WorldFAIR has received funding from the European Commission’s WIDERA coordination and support programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101058393. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

ABS	Australian Bureau of Statistics
ADA	Australian Data Archive
AES	Australian Election Study
API	Application Programming Interface
AUSSA	Australian Survey of Social Attitudes
AUSSI-ESS	Australian Social Survey International – European Social Survey
CDIF	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DDI-CDI	Data Documentation Initiative - Cross-Domain Interoperability
DRUM	Digital Representation of Units of Measure
ELSST	European Language Social Science Thesaurus
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESS	European Social Survey
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
ICPSR	Inter-University Consortium for Political and Social Research
IUSSP	International Union for the Scientific Study of Population
ISSP	International Social Survey Program
SDMX	Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange

SDR	Survey Data Recycling
SSSOM	Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings

Executive summary

The Social Surveys Work Package (WP06) of the WorldFAIR project is focussed on the improvement of FAIR practices in the management of harmonised content in cross-national social surveys. The first report from the Work Package (Deliverable 6.1) provided an overview of the practices of comparative (cross-national) social surveys, through case studies of: (1) the European Social Survey (ESS) and (2) a satellite study, the Australian Social Survey International – European Social Survey (AUSSI-ESS). The focus of Deliverable 6.2 was on three recommendations (Rs) from that first report - the use of the DDI Lifecycle and variable cascade (R6.1 and R6.2), and requirements for formal registries of variables and reusable content (R6.5). In Deliverable 6.2, we outlined a proposed workflow for the processing of data harmonisation of social surveys that takes account of the practical steps required to bring diverse content together in a machine-actionable way, and that could best take advantage of external registered, persistent content. This workflow considers the core steps involved in the harmonisation process, key issues that occur in the processing of data during this process, and potential resolutions of these issues.

This third report then picks up from the previous two to test out proof-of-concept implementations of the workflows outlined in the second WP report, to trial the use of standardised workflows based on registry services available at the Australian Data Archive (ADA) and Sikt through their respective Colectica registries. The workflow steps are piloted with another comparative social survey, the International Social Survey Program (ISSP), to evaluate the Cross-Cultural Survey Harmonisation workflow as a suitable process for machine-to-machine based survey harmonisation.

The pilot demonstrated that the CSH workflow established in Deliverable 6.2 and piloted here in Phase 3 of Work Package 6 appears to be a viable method for standardising and progressively automating the process of survey data harmonisation. The six-step workflow, based on well-established procedures in cross-cultural survey data, has been shown to be a suitable means of engaging with both human and machine-mediated processes. The development of the workflow based on Sikt and ADA processes for managing the harmonisation of ESS and AUSSI-ESS, and the piloting of the workflow with the similarly structured ISSP survey data. This suggests that the workflow itself may be well suited to projects of this type.

Having said this, the workflow pilot also shows that there is still a significant degree of human manual input required. To this end, the following recommendations are proposed coming out of this Phase 3 work:

1. Establishment of **standardised access controls** both to data and metadata registries, to limit the need for less technical users to navigate access control systems
2. Establishment of a **code repository** for interaction with social science metadata repositories.
3. Establishment of mechanisms for **reuse of conceptual variable and other reference metadata across the DDI** standards ecosystem. (It was not clear for example how to use or reference a conceptual variable in the Sikt ESS metadata registry within the ADA harmonisation tool)
4. Standardised practices and code libraries for the **creation of DDI resource packages** for external reuse (to facilitate the reuse in Recommendation 3).

Table of contents

Executive summary	5
1. Introduction	7
1.1. Structure of this report	8
2. The cross-cultural survey harmonisation workflow	9
2.1. Describing the CCSH workflow	9
2.2. Piloting the CCSH workflow	10
3. Harmonising the ISSP using the CCSH workflow	11
3.1. Importing data	12
3.2. Harmonise concepts	13
3.2.1. Determine the concept of interest to be harmonised	13
3.2.2. Establish the conceptual content to be used in the target variable	14
3.2.3. Establish the source variable(s)	14
3.3. Harmonise variable names	18
3.4. Harmonise variable codes and categories (labels)	19
3.4.1. Harmonise substantive values and 4.2 Harmonise sentinel and missing values	20
3.4.2. Transform source values to target values	23
3.5. Data type harmonisation	24
3.6. Document harmonisation process	25
3.7. Summarising the process	26
4. Recommendations	28
5. Bibliography	30

1. Introduction

The Social Surveys work package (WP06) of the WorldFAIR project is focussed on the improvement of FAIR practices in the management of harmonised content in cross-national social surveys.

The first report from this Work Package (Deliverable 6.1)¹ provided an overview of the practices of comparative (cross-national) social surveys, through case studies of: (1) the European Social Survey (ESS) and (2) a satellite study, the Australian Social Survey International – European Social Survey (AUSSI-ESS), and the current data management and harmonisation practices of the Australian Data Archive (ADA) and Sikt, the work package partners.

Six recommendations resulted from that initial assessment of current practice:

- Recommendation 6.1: The ADA should move to the use of the DDI Lifecycle Version 3.3.
- Recommendation 6.2: The ADA should adopt the use of the DDI Variable Cascade for the management of their time series and longitudinal content.
- Recommendation 6.3: The ADA and Sikt should undertake a pilot to test the use of common libraries and scripts in the processing of ESS and AUSSI-ESS content.
- Recommendation 6.4: A public repository of template scripts should be made available for reuse in processing other cross-national datasets.
- Recommendation 6.5: ADA and Sikt should establish formal registries of variables and other reusable metadata and content, and expose current internal content from these registries for reuse through API services.
- Recommendation 6.6: Where possible, common content such as harmonised variables and code mappings should be persistently identified and made available through such registries to enable standardised and reusable harmonisation practices.

The second work package report (Deliverable 6.2)² then explored the development of recommended practices for the management and processing of cross-national survey data for the establishment of harmonised social science datasets. Deliverable 6.2 outlined a proposed workflow for the processing of data harmonisation of social surveys that takes account of the practical steps required to bring diverse content together in a machine-actionable way, and that could best take advantage of externally registered, persistent content.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599652>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8308012>

This third and final report (Deliverable 6.3) focusses now on the piloting of the proposed workflow outlined in the previous phase. The purpose of this phase is to trial the workflow with existing ADA and Sikt registries and services, and to determine the viability of the workflow for future data harmonisation activities in cross-cultural social surveys.

1.1. Structure of this report

The report begins with a review of the key elements of the data harmonisation workflow, drawing on Deliverable 6.2. This workflow includes the specific processing stages that are applied to link two or more variables, and key data and metadata requirements that could be established to support these workflows.

The main section of the report provides a summary of pilot processing activities used to implement each of the workflow stages – sample scripts, tools and registries used to illustrate the process of data harmonisation between source and target data sources. The paper then concludes with a review of the overall workflow, and recommendations for future development of machine-to-machine based data harmonisation processing.

2. The cross-cultural survey harmonisation workflow

There is a long history of survey data harmonisation that has been established in the social sciences and in related domains such as health. Deliverables 6.1 and 6.2 provided an overview of this history and related workflows used in projects and data archives. Deliverable 6.2 then detailed a proposed workflow that could be adopted more generally for harmonisation processes used across datasets. This workflow, abbreviated hereafter as the CSH workflow (short for “cross cultural survey harmonisation”) includes six core stages, illustrated in Figure 1 and detailed further below.

Figure 1. The cross-cultural survey harmonisation workflow

2.1. Describing the CSH workflow

The six stages in our workflow, drawing on the work of Kołczyńska (2021) and Antal (2022) are as follows³:

³ A more detailed discussion of the workflow is included in Deliverable 6.2.

1. Import of data: accessing the source data to be harmonised from its storage location
2. Harmonise concepts: align the conceptual content contained in the instance variables in the source dataset(s) with the conceptual content in the target variable(s).
 - 2.1. Determine the concept of interest to be harmonised: detail the concept that is being defined and measured.
 - 2.2. Establish the conceptual content to be used in the target variable: locate the agreed target content in project documentation or (ideally) in a variable registry. If this is not available, establish an agreed target variable.
 - 2.3. Establish the source variable(s): locate the relevant variables in the source dataset(s) that are to be matched to the target variable. Again, this is preferably contained in an existing registry, but may be included within existing data or metadata files or project documentation.
3. Harmonise variable names: execute transformation code to change the variable names in the source dataset(s) to the target names in the destination dataset.
4. Harmonise variable codes and categories (labels).
 - 4.1. Harmonise substantive values: align the codes and categories associated with the substantive categories in the target variable and source variables.
 - 4.2. Harmonise sentinel and missing values: align the codes and categories used to manage non-sentinel content (e.g. categories denoting missing information, ineligibility to respond or non-applicability of the question) to target sentinel values.
 - 4.3. Transform source values to target values: execute transformation code to change the values of codes and categories in the source variable(s) to target values in the target variable.
5. Data type harmonisation: align the data type of newly generated target variables with the intended data type.
6. Document harmonisation process: capture information on the execution of the harmonisation workflow to capture the process that has been executed.

2.2. Piloting the CSH workflow

The proposed CSH workflow was established to provide a means of describing and standardising these harmonisation processes and code that could be made reusable using existing registries. A key outcome of this Phase 3 is to test the workflow with a survey harmonisation process, to determine whether it:

- a) suitably captures the required activities in the harmonisation process;
- b) can be used in conjunction with external metadata registries to enable reuse of FAIR metadata;
- c) can be automated through the use of standard code libraries.

The original intent in Phase 3 of the project was to evaluate the workflow in the harmonisation process of a new round of the Australian Social Survey International-ESS (AUSSI-ESS) with the most recent wave of the European Social Survey. Due to a change in circumstances in Australia, the new wave of AUSSI-ESS has not yet been collected. In addition, there have been some unexpected challenges with access to the Sikt ESS metadata repository through the Colectica API, due to the use of a single sign-on system. Given that this evaluation was intended only as a proof of concept test, it was determined that making changes to production systems was not appropriate for this project.

As such, it was decided to trial the CSSH workflow with the Australian data harmonisation with the International Social Survey Programme – another long-running comparative social survey that has run since 1984 and in which both Sikt and ADA are participants⁴. The ISSP shares a number of similar features to the ESS in terms of content and harmonisation practices, and the project teams for ISSP and ESS are often the same in many countries. Notably however, the ISSP does not have a metadata registry. For the purposes of this evaluation, we have instead established a demonstration metadata repository for the ISSP 2021 wave in the ADA AUSIRISS metadata repository⁵.

The second decision that was made for piloting the workflow was the use of a mix of software tools and services for testing. The development of the workflow in Deliverable 6.2 had proposed the use of the R “Harmonization” package for implementing the workflow activities. However in testing the package in Phase 3, it was found that there were a number of challenges in working with missing data. As such, the choice was made to use instead software or programming tools suited to the particular stage in the CCSH workflow.

⁴ For details of the ISSP project, see <https://www.issp.org>

⁵ The ADA staging repository is located at: <https://mdr-staging.ausiriss.org.au>

3. Harmonising the ISSP using the CCSH workflow

The remainder of the report provides an overview of the stages of the ISSP data harmonisation process as implemented using the CCSH workflow and current and new tools and workflows. Each stage of the CCSH process is described below, with a summary of requirements for each stage, and including procedures used to undertake the harmonisation. It was not possible or intended to implement a complete workflow automation in this phase of the project, but rather to establish the usefulness of standard processing methods and external registries for streamlining and improving the harmonisation process. As such, the process uses a combination of manual and automated processing tools at each stage and makes recommendations for further tools and process development at the end of the project.

3.1. Importing data

The Australian source data for the ISSP is drawn from the Australian Survey of Social Attitudes. This AuSSA 2021 data is accessible from the ADA website⁶, and each dataset has a published DOI minted by Datacite⁷.

The data is available in multiple formats, but for the purposes of the evaluation, the SPSS format (commonly used in ADA and Sikt data processing) is used here. The data can be downloaded from ADA with a standard approval process and then using an API key. Following extraction of the zip file, the data is accessible to use in statistical packages such as SPSS and R. A sample script importing and then subsetting and saving the source variables from the AuSSA dataset is included in the Additional Materials for this project from the ADA website⁸.

Metadata import for the ISSP is somewhat more challenging, as there is no ISSP metadata registry to draw from. The ISSP coordinating team and the ISSP archive at GESIS do provide PDF format descriptions of the questionnaire and variables to be included in the survey, as well as template SPSS scripts that can be used to generate variables and data files. For the ISSP 2021 Health module, the questionnaire is available to the public⁹, while the template processing script is accessible to coordinating country teams through the ISSP members' website¹⁰. This processing script can be used to generate a template "shell" SPSS data file as a target data source.

⁶ <https://dataverse.ada.edu.au/file.xhtml?fileId=18392&version=2.0#>

⁷ <http://dx.doi.org/10.26193/AH8VKX>

⁸ <http://dx.doi.org/10.26193/AWVJTI>

⁹ https://issp.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/ISSP2021_final-source-questionnaire.pdf

¹⁰ <https://issp.org/members/member-area/>

3.2. Harmonise concepts

Task: align the conceptual content contained in the instance variables in the source dataset(s) with the conceptual content in the target variable(s).

3.2.1. Determine the concept of interest to be harmonised

Sub-task: detail the concept that is being defined and measured.

The content of the ISSP data collection for each wave is determined in advance, evaluated and voted on by the ISSP member nations, and distributed to the ISSP national teams. The concepts to be measured are included in the project documentation for the wave, along with the approved questionnaire and dataset templates. An example of the guidelines for the variable “SEX” are included below in Figure 2.

SEX “Sex of respondent”

1. Measurement goal

Sex of the respondent

2. Filtering questions/respondent universe

Ask all.

3. Variable definition/code list

SEX “Sex of respondent”

1	Male
2	Female
-9	No answer

4. Example question text(s)

Are you...

1	Male
2	Female

5. Coding & classification instructions

-

6. Other comments

Information can be collected by interviewer observation in face-to-face interviews, by direct question with other interview modes or it can be derived from the sampling list (e.g. for samples drawn with sufficient information from population registers).

Figure 2: ISSP Background variable guidelines for the variable “SEX”.

The ISSP harmonised dataset includes three groups of variables:

- A set of **administrative variables** used to manage the collection and describe the country and method-specific information.
- The core set of **topic-specific measures** to be included in the topic for the survey wave. In 2022, the core topic was Health. The core included repeat collection of a number of the questions included in the 2012 wave, along with a set of new questions. In some years (including 2021), a set of optional measures on the topic are also included.
- A set of **background variables** describing the participant's demography, education, work and political preferences, along with details of their partner, family and housing situation (where applicable).

3.2.2. Establish the conceptual content to be used in the target variable

Sub-task: locate the agreed target content in project documentation or (ideally) in a variable registry. If this is not available, establish an agreed target variable.

The ISSP does not have a machine-accessible external registry for the conceptual content included in target variables. It does, however, define conceptual and represented variables ahead of time in the template SPSS scripts including variable names and labels, codes and categories, and missing/sentinel values.

To generate the target variables for use in the ISSP pilot, the template SPSS script was used to generate an empty SPSS dataset which was then ingested into the Colectica registry. DDI instance variables also inherit all the properties of the DDI variable cascade (including Conceptual and Represented Variables). The instance variables in the empty ingested empty dataset can then be used to generate conceptual variables and variable groups. However within the Colectica registry, conceptual variables must be separately defined and then concorded with instance variables. (This step is completed in Step 3.2.3 below).

3.2.3. Establish the source variable(s)

Sub-task: locate the relevant variables in the source dataset(s) that are to be matched to the target variable. Again, this is preferably contained in an existing registry, but may be included within existing data or metadata files or project documentation.

The selection of source variables for harmonisation with the target can vary in complexity depending on the number and diversity of the variables that are candidates for matching. Matching

of variables for the ISSP and AUSSI-ESS harmonisation, however, is mostly straightforward as the data collection activities and resultant source datasets are designed as inputs for an *ex ante* output harmonisation (Wolf et al., 2017). In many instances, there is a one-to-one correspondence of source and target variables, or a planned re-coding of source content into a target variable *ex ante*.

In practical terms, this then means that the mapping of source to target variables can be completed in a relatively straightforward manner with the use of a spreadsheet. The Colectica metadata registry also allows for this variable mapping to be used as a concordance file to establish the relationship between conceptual, represented and instance variables in the registry. A spreadsheet mapping the AuSSA source variables to the ISSP target variables was thus generated, and ingested into the Colectica registry. A sample of the concordance sheet, also posted in a Dataverse repository¹¹, is included in Figure 3 below. Details of the ingest process used within Colectica are included in the Colectica help site¹².

Name	Label	Topic	ISSP_2021_	ISSP_2021_AU_Source_Dataset
v69	Q34a_OPT Most people become very overweight because they are lazy	ISSP 2021 He v69		A34_A
v70	Q34b_OPT Most people contracted Covid-19 because they were careless	ISSP 2021 He v70		A34_B
SEX	Sex of Respondent	ISSP Backgro SEX		I1
BIRTH	Year of birth	ISSP Backgro BIRTH		I2
AGE	Age of respondent	ISSP Backgro AGE		
EDUCYRS	Years of full-time schooling	ISSP Backgro EDUCYRS		I4
AU_ISCD	Country specific highest completed degree of education: Australia	ISSP Backgro AU_ISCD		
ISCED	ISCED 2011: highest completed degree of education [merged variable]	ISSP Backgro ISCED		
EDULEVEL	ISCED 2011 simplified: highest completed degree of education	ISSP Backgro EDULEVEL		
WORK	Currently, formerly, or never in paid work	ISSP Backgro WORK		I7
WRKHRS	Hours worked weekly	ISSP Backgro WRKHRS		I8
EMPREL	Employment relationship	ISSP Backgro EMPREL		I9
WRKSUP	Supervise other employees	ISSP Backgro WRKSUP		I12
NSUP	Number of other employees supervised	ISSP Backgro NSUP		I12other
TYPORG1	Type of organisation, for-profit/non-profit	ISSP Backgro TYPORG1		I13
TYPORG2	Type of organisation, public/private	ISSP Backgro TYPORG2		I14
ISCO08	Occupation ISCO 2008	ISSP Backgro ISCO08		I15ISCO084
MAINSTAT	Main status	ISSP Backgro MAINSTAT		I18
PARTLIV	Living in steady partnership	ISSP Backgro PARTLIV		I19
SPWORK	Spouse, partner: currently, formerly or never in paid work	ISSP Backgro SPWORK		I20
SPWRKHRS	Spouse, partner: hours worked weekly	ISSP Backgro SPWRKHRS		I21
SPEMPREL	Spouse, partner: employment relationship	ISSP Backgro SPEMPREL		I22
SPWRKSUP	Spouse, partner: supervise other employees	ISSP Backgro SPWRKSUP		I23
SPISCO08	Spouse, partner: occupation ISCO 2008	ISSP Backgro SPISCO08		I24ISCO084
SPMAINST	Spouse, partner: main status	ISSP Backgro SPMAINST		I27
UNION	Trade union membership	ISSP Backgro UNION		I28

Figure 3: ISSP Concordance File for Australian source data to ISSP target dataset

¹¹ Additional Materials available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.26193/AWVJT>

¹² <https://docs.colectica.com/designer/import/concordance/#variable-concordance-definition-files>

It should be noted that while the above variable mapping was generated manually, it should be relatively straightforward to generate a user interface to build this mapping. (This is explored further below in Section 3.4, where a pilot service for mapping codes and categories has been developed.)

Once the concordance is ingested and published in the Colectica registry, there are now externally machine-accessible conceptual variables (and optionally also conceptual variable groups) that can be used in external applications. The concordance also includes referencing to the internal source and target variable names (through the column headers, which refer to DDI Datasets). From this, the full URN, `ConceptualVariableName` and `Label` of the variable could be readily derived from the internal reference once the `ConceptualVariable` and `InstanceVariable` relationships have been registered in the Colectica registry.

A sample of the conceptual variables generated in the ADA Colectica registry for the ISSP Background group is included in Figure 4 below. These are taken from the newly registered `Conceptual Variable Group`, which also has a unique identifier and a DDI URN, as do each of the conceptual variables contained within the group. An example of the `Conceptual Variable` “SEX” is also included in Figure 5.

MDR Staging Search Explore Admin Help Baskets 1

ISSP Background

ISSP 2021 Harmonisation ISSP_AU_2021_Concordance_File_V1.xlsx ISSP 2021 Harmonisation

Conceptual Variable Group

Label ISSP Background

Subjects

Keywords

Conceptual Variables

Name	Label
SEX	Sex of Respondent
BIRTH	Year of birth
AGE	Age of respondent
EDUCYRS	Years of full-time schooling
AU_ISCD	Country specific highest completed degree of education: Australia
ISCED	ISCED 2011: highest completed degree of education [merged variable]
EDULEVEL	ISCED 2011 simplified: highest completed degree of education
WORK	Currently, formerly, or never in paid work
WRKHRS	Hours worked weekly
EMPREL	Employment relationship

Figure 4: Conceptual variable group for ISSP Background Variables (Source: <https://mdr-staging.ausiriss.org.au/item/au.ausiriss/3ba6a667-568e-4cd0-9dc5-618f0a0bb105>)

Sex of Respondent

ISSP_AU_2021_Concordance_File_V1.xlsx ISSP Background

The screenshot shows a web interface with a dark blue header containing 'MDR Staging Search Explore Admin'. Below the header, the title 'Sex of Respondent' is displayed, followed by two file icons and labels: 'ISSP_AU_2021_Concordance_File_V1.xlsx' and 'ISSP Background'. The main content area has a light grey background and a toolbar with icons for menu, share, info, refresh, and download. The 'Information' section is highlighted with a horizontal line and contains the following details:

- Agency**: au.ausiriss
- Identifier**: d763f405-a252-4e45-9001-d91310847d48
- Version**: 1
- DDI URN**: urn:ddi:au.ausiriss:d763f405-a252-4e45-9001-d91310847d48:1
- Last Updated**: Friday, February 9, 2024
- Storage Format**: DDI 3.3

Figure 5: Conceptual variable group for ISSP Background Variables (Source: <https://mdr-staging.ausiriss.org.au/item/au.ausiriss/d763f405-a252-4e45-9001-d91310847d48>)

3.3. Harmonise variable names

Task: execute transformation code to change the variable names in the source dataset(s) to the target names in the destination dataset.

With the availability of the source-target concordance file, the generation of the transformation of source variable names to target variable names is a standard activity in most statistical packages. A script for transforming variable names is included in the Additional Materials package for the project¹³, and a sample of the script is included below in Figure 6. This script was generated using a

¹³ Materials Dataset DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.26193/AWVJTI>

simple Excel concatenation function, and such a script could be automatically generated from a concordance file using standard text functions in the relevant language¹⁴.


```

1 * Encoding: UTF-8.
2 ** SPSS syntax file to transform variable names **
3 ** Cross-cultural Survey Harmonisation Step 3 **
4 GET FILE='C:/Users/u4777429/Documents/Steve/ADA Data/ISSP/ISSP_2021/ISSP_AU_Source_Dataset.sav'.
5
6
7 RENAME VARIABLES (A1 = v1) .
8 RENAME VARIABLES (A2 = v2) .
9 RENAME VARIABLES (A3 = v3) .
10 RENAME VARIABLES (A4_A = v4) .
11 RENAME VARIABLES (A4_B = v5) .
12 RENAME VARIABLES (A4_C = v6) .
13 RENAME VARIABLES (A5 = v7) .
14 RENAME VARIABLES (A6_A = v8) .
15 RENAME VARIABLES (A6_B = v9) .
16 RENAME VARIABLES (A7_A = v10) .
17 RENAME VARIABLES (A7_B = v11) .
18 RENAME VARIABLES (A7_C = v12) .
19 RENAME VARIABLES (A7_D = v13) .
20 RENAME VARIABLES (A8_A = v14) .
21 RENAME VARIABLES (A8_B = v15) .
22 RENAME VARIABLES (A8_C = v16) .
23 RENAME VARIABLES (A8_D = v17) .
24 RENAME VARIABLES (A9 = v18) .
25 RENAME VARIABLES (A10_A = v19) .
26 RENAME VARIABLES (A10_B = v20) .
27 RENAME VARIABLES (A10_C = v21) .
28 RENAME VARIABLES (A11 = v22) .
29 RENAME VARIABLES (A12_A = v23) .
30 RENAME VARIABLES (A12_B = v24) .
31 RENAME VARIABLES (A12_C = v25) .
32 RENAME VARIABLES (A13_A = v26) .
33 RENAME VARIABLES (A13_B = v27) .
34 RENAME VARIABLES (A14_A = v28) .
35 RENAME VARIABLES (A14_B = v29) .

```

Figure 6: Sample SPSS variable name harmonisation script – CESH Workflow Step 3

3.4. Harmonise variable codes and categories (labels)

The process of harmonising variable codes and categories (known collectively as code lists) is perhaps the most time-consuming and challenging part of the harmonisation process. This process requires a one-to-one mapping of each of the category values in the source variable to the target categories in the target variable, and subsequent alignment of the internal code denoting that category. As detailed in Deliverable 6.2, there can be four sources of difference creating mismatches:

- a) Differences in categories using the same code.
- b) Difference in codes denoting the same category.

¹⁴ The Australian Data Archive has produced a script generation tool for the transformation of codes and categories in Section 3.5 which could be adapted for this purpose.

- c) Differences in both codes and categories.
- d) Matching codes and categories but different encoding (e.g. data type differences).

3.4.1. Harmonise substantive values and 4.2 Harmonise sentinel and missing values

Sub-task 4.1: align the codes and categories associated with the substantive categories in the target variable and source variables.

Sub-task 4.2: align the codes and categories used to manage non-sentinel content (e.g. categories denoting missing information, ineligibility to respond or non-applicability of the question) to target sentinel values.

The alignment of the codes and categories in a variable can be completed using the creation of a simple matrix, with target codes and categories along the rows, and equivalent codes from the source variables in subsequent columns. This matrix allows the cross-comparison of codes and categories between source and target, and then the generation of scripts to transform values from source to target in the preferred data management language (in this evaluation, we are using SPSS).

Two core challenges, however, were identified in the process of creating these harmonisation matrices:

- a) The variation in processing of missing and sentinel values between data formats required significant iteration to identify and resolve format errors.
- b) The accumulation of small variations in both codes and categories created large matrices which were both challenging to read and difficult to automatically process.

The first problem of variations in the treatment of missing values was addressed by mapping target content values into explicit codes and categories, rather than “special” formats handled by the relevant software package. This does require then “resetting” the missing formats at a later stage in the process – a step that is now handled in Step 5 of the CSH workflow. This choice separates the identification of the sentinel or missing status from its software-specific treatment, which we see as a significant benefit.

The second problem of the growth in the size of the matrix was addressed by establishing a more detailed process. Within this, three stages are now used to generate these mappings:

1. Production of a first-stage matrix including all source variable codes and categories (source matrix) – generated by Colectica.
2. Selection of a target code list (code and category combination) and generation of a “shell” harmonisation matrix (target matrix).
3. Adding each of the source matrix values into the target matrix.

The first version of these mappings was completed manually to determine a preferred form and process for building the target matrix. This process is however slow and prone to coding errors, and also results in loss of identifier information. A sample of the hand-generated mapping is included below in Figure 7.

	A	B	C	D	E
1					
2	Name				
3	SEX				
4	Label				
5	Sex				
6					
7	SOURCE MATRIX				
8					
9	Item Name	ISSP 2021 Harmonisation			
10		ISSP 2021 Au	ISSP 2021 Target		
11		ISSP_2021_A	ISSP_2021_Target_Dataset		
12		I1	SEX		
13	No answer			-9	
14	Male	1		1	
15	Female	2		2	
16					
17					
18	TARGET MATRIX				
19			ISSP 2021 Au	ISSP 2021 Target	
20	Target name	sex	ISSP_2021_A	ISSP_2021_Target_Dataset	
21	Target category	Target code	I1	SEX	
22	Not asked	-9			
23	Blank	-4			
24	No response	-3			
25	Skipped	-2			
26	Missing	-1			
27	No response	-3		-9	
28	Male	1		1	1
29	Female	2		2	2
30	Other	3			
31					
32					
33					
34					

Figure 7: Sample manually generated source and target value mapping matrices for variable “SEX”.

This process did however provide a template for a semi-automated method for generating these matrices. Using the newly-created instance variables now available in the registry, which were generated in Step 2 of the workflow, it was now possible to build the source matrix automatically using python scripting to access the Colectica APIs, which enables access to all the DDI-Lifecycle registry information. It was also possible to generate a form of the second target matrix, although this is complicated by the selection of the target codelist which requires further rearrangement of the matrix content.

The automation of the harmonisation matrix generation and manipulation does however appear viable. We have been able to establish a proof of concept tool - https://bit.ly/harmonisation_demo - that can generate both source and target matrices, and output them in a form which can be used in data transformation¹⁵. The next effort in this tool development will be an interactive tool to allow the editing of the cells of the matrix, to allow the user to map their preferred source-target combinations.

Notably, it has also been possible to test the potential use of machine-learning methods for matching code and category combinations, although the results have been mixed thus far¹⁶. This option does have significant promise, as the provision of recommended or ideally automated matches would significantly speed up what is the slowest phase in the harmonisation process.

3.4.2. Transform source values to target values

Sub-task: execute transformation code to change the values of codes and categories in the source variable(s) to target values in the target variable.

Having established the target matrix structure as a spreadsheet, it is then straightforward to generate scripts to transform the data based on the matrix structure. To this end, a script generator developed for the ANZLEAD service¹⁷ to harmonise the Australian Election Study has been adapted for use with the ISSP harmonisation tables¹⁸. This R script¹⁹ reads the content of the autogenerated target matrix, generated either by hand or through the proof of concept tool in 3.4.1 above, and

¹⁵ A permanent URL for this tool, and the code for the tool will be released at a future date. The code for the tool is currently in a private GitHub repository as it is being developed, at <https://github.com/ADA-ANU/ADA-Harmonisation>

¹⁶ In two examples using ISSP variables, the algorithm is aligning “Very happy” with “Very unhappy”, and “Not at all” with “No response”.

¹⁷ <https://lead.anu.edu.au>

¹⁸ https://github.com/ADA-ANU/ADA_Research_Data_Tools/tree/main/AES%20harmonising

¹⁹ Additional materials, including a sample R script, are available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.26193/AWVJTI>

generates a data transformation script to generate harmonised SPSS files. Having followed through the steps of the CCSH workflow, these files are now harmonised with target variable names, labels and code lists.

3.5. Data type harmonisation

Sub-task: align the data type of newly generated target variables with the intended data type.

Deliverable 6.2 identified a series of data type attributes available in the DDI Lifecycle specification²⁰ that could be used to standardise data typing of variables. These attributes include:

- **RecommendedDataType:** either a term or reference to an established controlled vocabulary list (preferably from W3C XML Schema Part 2 list of data types);
- **GenericOutputFormat:** specification for the preferred output format expressed in a generic way;
- **@missingValue:** an array of values that should be treated as missing values;
- **@blankIsMissingValue:** Boolean attribute indicating that a blank (no content) should be treated as a missing value;
- **@classificationLevel:** specifying the classification of the content as: Nominal, Ordinal, Interval, Ratio, or Continuous.

The data type harmonisation process has not yet been tested in the pilot project due to time constraints. It is possible however to set some of the Data Type attributes through suitable formatting of the ingested Target Dataset.

- **Missing values:** In the processing of standard codes and categories, particularly for missing and sentinel values (3.4.2 above), it was found to be beneficial to remove internal ‘format-specific’ missing value handling from variables and to explicitly code these values. Within SPSS and most statistical packages, scripts can be used to set valid missing and sentinel values and classification levels, and most software services also allow for setting of the handling of missing values within their software. As such, it may be preferable to avoid setting missing values until the output format of the dataset is determined. Indeed, in the testing of the Harmonisation R package, it was the maintenance and transformation of missing values which caused significant errors in the process.

²⁰ <https://ddialliance.org/Specification/DDI-Lifecycle/>

- **Classification level:** the use of classification levels of a variable is somewhat varied, and not all statistical packages use standard terms and definitions. Where available, however, these levels can generally be set using internal scripting languages for the relevant package.

3.6. Document harmonisation process

Task: Capture information on the execution of the harmonisation workflow to capture the process that has been executed.

The creation of documentation is often left as an afterthought in the conduct of many data processing activities, including the harmonisation process. As such, the capture of documentation should ideally occur as part of the process rather than after the fact.

In this regard, the execution of the CCSH pilot has been able to generate some degree of documentation as a byproduct of executing the process itself. The use of software scripts and external registries in the piloting of this harmonisation process resulted in artefacts which reflect the workflow process undertaken.

There is, however, a more integrated approach that could be taken here. For example, this documentation could be further enhanced through the automated generation of log outputs in the execution of scripts or automation tools. A first attempt to do this has been incorporated in the python Harmonisation tool, which generates a “Harmonisation Decision” table when it generates a machine-learning generated Target Harmonisation Matrix (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Harmonisation decision documentation in the ADA Harmonisation tool

The matrix mappings themselves could also be effectively mapped using a mapping standard. Recent work in the WorldFAIR project has been evaluating the use of SSSOM as a potential standard for this. A further enhancement to the Harmonisation tool could be to automatically generate SSSOM as a documented output of the tool.

3.7. Summarising the process

What then can be made of the overall workflow process proposed for cross-cultural survey harmonisation? Figure 9 provides a summary of the overall process and the relative success of standardisation and automation efforts in each step of the workflow.

Figure 9: Success in standardisation and automation in the CESH workflow

Looking at each of the steps, there has been reasonable success in the capacity to streamline this harmonisation workflow. Overall, there were no stages in the workflow that did not demonstrate some capacity for scripting and automation, and particularly steps 2 to 4 demonstrate the capacity for input of metadata from registries, passing through to either (web or software) applications or auto-generated scripts, and then returning generated outputs to a data repository and/or metadata registry. While Step 5 was not evaluated, the availability of scripting methods for establishing data formats and attributes suggests that this should also be a viable option.

The two steps where further improvement could be required were at the start and end of the workflow – data import and process documentation. Considering each of these in turn:

- Data and metadata import was largely limited by the access and authorisation controls that are placed on the repositories. Both the Colectica metadata registries at ADA and Sikt, as well as the Dataverse repository used by ADA for data file dissemination, provide open

human access to variable metadata. By comparison, machine-to-machine access (whether by script or API calls) is restricted by authentication requirements which may impact on reuse. While standard methods for authentication exist, they will need to be made relatively easy to negotiate by both machine and human users.

- With regard to process documentation, the use of executable scripts to generate and manage data and metadata forms a type of documentation in and of itself. More automated documentation creation would however be of significant benefit, and should be achievable through relatively simple automated logging of script outputs.

4. Recommendations

Section 3.7 has demonstrated that the CCSH workflow established in Deliverable 6.2 and piloted here in Phase 3 of Work Package 6 appears to be a viable method for standardising and progressively automating the process of survey data harmonisation. The six-step workflow, based on well-established procedures in cross-cultural survey data, has been shown to be a suitable means of engaging with both human and machine-mediated processes. The development of the workflow was based on Sikt and ADA processes for managing the harmonisation of ESS and AUSSI-ESS, and the piloting of the workflow has been assessed with the similarly structured ISSP survey data. This suggests that the workflow itself may be well suited to projects of this type.

Having said this, the workflow pilot also showed that there is a high degree of human manual input required. The manual manipulation of the code harmonisation matrices in Section 3.4.1/2 for example suggest that there is more work that can be done to make the most of machine-to-machine integration between software systems and metadata registries.

To this end, the following recommendations are proposed coming out of this Phase 3 work. Two recommendations are aimed at **social science data archives**, as well as **providers of related data and metadata registries** and **repositories that might host relevant data and metadata**.

1. Establishment of **standardised access controls** both to data and metadata registries, to limit the need for less technical users to navigate access control systems. (Recommendation type: Technical (data); Technical (metadata), organisational, policy).
2. Establishment of a **code repository** for interaction with social science metadata repositories. (Recommendation type: Technical (data); Technical (metadata)).

A further two recommendations are focussed on **the DDI Alliance and user community** to better support reuse of DDI metadata and registries.

3. Establishment of technical and/or policy mechanisms for **reuse of conceptual variable and other reference metadata across the DDI standards ecosystem**. (It was not clear for example how to use or reference a conceptual variable in the Sikt ESS metadata registry within the ADA harmonisation tool). (Recommendation type: Technical (metadata), policy).
4. Standardised practices and code libraries for the **creation of DDI resource packages** for external reuse (to facilitate the reuse in Recommendation 3). (Recommendation type: Technical (metadata), policy).

5. Bibliography

- Antal D (2022). retroharmonize: Ex Post Survey Data Harmonization. R package version 0.2.5.002, <https://retroharmonize.dataobservatory.eu/>
- Kończyńska, M. (2022). Combining multiple survey sources: A reproducible workflow and toolbox for survey data harmonization. *Methodological Innovations*, 15(1), 62-72. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20597991221077923>
- McEachern, S., Orten, H., Thome Petersen, H., & Perry, R. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D6.1) Cross-national Social Sciences survey FAIR implementation case studies (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7599652>
- McEachern, S., Orten, H., Perry, R., & Strand, K. (2023). WorldFAIR (D6.2) Cross-national Social Sciences survey best practice guidelines (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8308012>
- Wilkinson, M.D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I.J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L.B., Bourne, P.E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A.J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C.T., Finkers, R., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gray, A.J.G., Groth, P., Goble, C., Grethe, J.S., Heringa, J., 't Hoen, P.A.C., Hooft, R., Kuhn, T., Kok, R., Kok, J., Lusher, S.J., Martone, M.E., Mons, A., Packer, A.L., Persson, B., Rocca-Serra, P., Roos, M., van Schaik, R., Sansone, S.-A., Schultes, E., Sengstag, T., Slater, T., Strawn, G., Swertz, M.A., Thompson, M., van der Lei, J., van Mulligen, E., Velterop, J., Waagmeester, A., Wittenburg, P., Wolstencroft, K., Zhao, J., Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Wolf C, Schneider SL, Behr D, Joye, D. (2016). Harmonizing survey questions between cultures and over time. In: Wolf C, Joye, D., Smith, T. and Fu, Y. (eds) *The SAGE Handbook of Survey Methodology*. Los Angeles, CA: SAGE, pp.502–524.